

**THE IMPORTANCE AND INFLUENCE OF
HUMAN CAPITAL (TEACHING STAFF) FOR
THE ROMANIAN PRE-UNIVERSITY EDUCATIONAL
SYSTEM FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF
COMMUNICATION IN THE EDUCATIONAL
ENVIRONMENT DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC**

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Abstract

The article addresses the importance and influence of human capital (teaching staff) for the Romanian pre-university educational system from the perspective of communication in the educational environment during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The phrase researched includes the importance of information sources for the organization of school activity, the clarity of information received regarding the organization of school activity, the ways in which teachers were informed about the teaching process and other relevant aspects during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this sense, the results of a research carried out in 2021 among Romanian pre-university education teachers are presented.

Keywords: *information sources; clarity of information received; online communication tools;*

Context

Among the "flagship initiatives" of the European Union for the current time horizon, "increasing the skills level of the workforce" is correlated with the field of education and training.

The initiative is approached in Romania from the perspective of improving the education system.

SGG of Romania (2020), taking over the directions of the Europe 2020 Strategy, states that "if 3% of GDP will be invested in Research and Development, we should ensure that we have researchers".

This is just one of the measures envisaged for the pre-university sector, the approach being integrated and including investments in the *reform of continuing professional training and teacher evaluation*.

According to an analysis of the American Chamber of Commerce (AmCham Romania, 2021), "the adaptation of teachers' skills and abilities to the specific educational needs of an increasingly dynamic and digitized society" is necessary.

The measure is required due to the systemic problems identified by the analysis: the school dropout rate, the students' results in national and international assessments, the functional illiteracy rate, etc.

The impact of the efficiency of human capital in Romanian education is not only immediate. This reality places Romania last in the European Union in terms of human capital development in the DESI 2020 index (Digital Economy and Society Index).

The crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted a series of vulnerabilities of the pre-university education system in Romania. Among them, the precariousness of digital skills among teachers and students.

Developing digital skills is an imperative priority. It is a measure found during the period of the COVID-19 pandemic and post-pandemic and decided by the Digital Education Agenda of the European Union.

AmCham (2021) regards as the main measure "the adoption of new technologies in the didactic activity, supplemented by ensuring their use and ensuring connectivity to the Internet". The context of the proposed measures is a complex one, "the digitization of education contributing to reducing inequities in the system and improving access to education for students from different backgrounds".

1. Study on the changes in pre-university education during the COVID-19 pandemic and in the post-pandemic period

The Council of the European Union in regards to combating the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic in education and training (2020) states that "school closures have been a particular challenge for socio-economically disadvantaged learners".

Therefore, "teachers had to adapt quickly from face-to-face teaching to distance teaching." This, "even if not all teachers had the

necessary experience, knowledge, skills and competences to organize and carry out distance learning activities effectively".

The Council of Europe Recommendations (2020) aim to "support the further development of digital skills and competences of teachers and trainers to facilitate teaching and assessment in digital learning environments". These must be accompanied by "accelerating the digital transformation of education and training systems, boost the digital capacity of education and training institutions and reduce the digital divide".

Both in the analyzes carried out and in the recommendations made regarding the lessons of the pandemic for the field of education, the main measures target human capital, the teaching staff. All support measures are focused on this type of capital, with priority, both during the pandemic caused by COVID-19 and as perspectives, in the post-pandemic period.

Starting from the elements reported regarding the COVID-19 pandemic at the European level in the field of education and training, the study *Online school and challenges during the pandemic* in Romanian pre-university education is carried out.

The general objective of the study is to evaluate the communication sources for the organization of school activity during the COVID-19 pandemic. The secondary objectives investigate how to implement the teaching process, the support offered to students for teaching activities during the pandemic.

To carry out the study *Online school and its challenges during the pandemic*, the quantitative method was based on a questionnaire that included 25 items and was applied through the Google Forms platform.

Starting from the research objectives, the study aims to validate two research hypotheses:

H 1. There are significant differences in *communication during the COVID-19 pandemic*, depending on the environment in which the school is located, the type of funding, the teaching degree, the level of education, management positions and the number of employees in the educational unit.

H 2. There are significant differences in *the teaching process during the COVID-19 pandemic*, depending on the environment in which the school is located, the type of funding, the teaching degree, the level of education, management positions and the number of employees in the educational unit.

1.1. Research methodology

The questionnaire was applied to a number of 522 *teachers*, of which 298 *teach in urban schools*, and 224 *teach in rural schools*. Depending on the type of funding, 463 of the teachers teach in schools with state funding, and 59 teachers teach in schools with private funding. Depending on the level of education, 71 teachers teach at the pre-primary level, 128 teach at the primary level, 227 teach at the secondary level and 96 teach at the high school level. Depending on the didactic degree, 33 of the teachers are beginners, 83 of the teachers are permanent, 91 have the didactic degree II and 315 have the didactic degree I.

Regarding whether or not they have a management position, 102 *teachers are principals or deputy principals*, and 420 *do not have a management position*.

Depending on the number of employees in the units where they work, 54 *respondents work in educational units with less than 20 teaching staff*. 269 *respondents work in educational units with a number between 21 and 50 teaching staff*. 161 *respondents work in educational units with between 51 and 100 teaching staff*. 38 *respondents work in educational units with more than 100 teaching staff*.

The profile of the respondents made up of the preponderances found in the sample is: teaching staff from the urban environment (57.1%), from a state education unit (88.7%), with a number of employees between 21-50 (51.5 %), who teach at the secondary education level (43.5%), with teaching degree I (60.3%), teaching staff, without management position (80.5%).

For the development of a research model that validates the defined hypotheses, the variables were selected based on similar studies previously presented (Strategy Europe 2020, analysis of the American Chamber of Commerce in Romania (2021), Agenda for digital education of the European Union, IRES study (2020).

The dependent variables of the study are represented by: *Communication during the COVID-19 pandemic; Teaching process during the COVID-19 pandemic*. The independent variables of the study are: *The environment in which the school is located: urban, rural; Type of financing: state, private; Didactic degree: beginner, final, degree II, degree I; Education level: pre-primary, primary, secondary, high school; Position:*

director/deputy director, teacher; *The number of employees in the educational unit*: less than 20, between 21-50, between 51-100, over 100.

1.2 Research results

The statistical analysis of the results was carried out by means of the statistical program SPSS.20. According to Labăr (2008), statistical techniques are used depending on the purpose of the research and the usefulness of the information.

Frequency analysis is used for information on absolute frequency (how many times the value appears within the distribution of responses - frequency). Labăr (2008) states that frequency analysis "helps in describing the composition of the sample on which the research was carried out, being a useful statistical operation for describing the percentages of subjects who chose different forms of response to an item".

The independent samples t-test is used "to test for significant differences between two compared groups on the means of the dependent variable" (Labăr, 2008)).

Simple ANOVA (One-Way) analysis of variance tests for differences between the means of three or more independent groups. Labăr (2008) presents the application of the One-Way ANOVA method "when an Independent Variable is nominal or ordinal, with three or more categories, in checking the effect of an Independent Variable on a Dependent Variable for intergroup design".

The chi-square test of association/independence is used to "test the association between two nominal, categorical variables or compare frequencies between two independent samples" (*ibidem*, 109).

According to Labăr (2008), the *Bonferroni Test* presents "equality of variances, the option being based on the reduced number of categories of the Independent Variable (V.I)".

1.3 Discussions

The interpretation of the data collected through the conducted study opens up a number of discussions regarding the human resource in Romanian pre-university education.

It includes teaching staff, school managers, students, their parents, central or local authorities involved in the teaching process.

In this sense, the presented study provides eloquent and sufficient data (in terms of the number of respondents and their representativeness as a sample) to generate conclusions of general value.

Regarding the human capital for the Romanian pre-university educational system, the research looked at the category of teaching and management staff.

Regarding the dynamics of the dependent variables and the hypotheses subject to validation, they have been included in two areas of analysis in which they can surprise by their importance and influence. They are the communication between the institutions involved in the didactic process, during the pandemic period and the implementation of the teaching process.

The data presented and interpreted fully validate the hypotheses pursued by the research.

The conclusions can be structured in two directions of analysis, starting from the structure proposed by the presented study:

A. the importance and influence of human capital for the Romanian pre-university educational system from the perspective of *communication during the pandemic period*;

B. the importance and influence of human capital for the Romanian pre-university educational system from the perspective of the *didactic process during the COVID-19 pandemic*.

It should be noted that these directions of analysis can be complementary to two others, important for understanding the need for digitization of education from the perspective of sustainable dimensions. They are the support for students who do not have the opportunity to participate in online courses/teaching activities and the reopening of schools during the pandemic.

Conclusions

A. Communication during the COVID-19 pandemic

Communication during the COVID-19 pandemic aims to identify the main sources, the methods and degree of information, the clarity of the information received, the authorities involved, *depending on the environment in which the school is located, the type of funding, the level of education, the managerial function.*

Depending on the independent variable, *the environment in which the school is located*, IŞJ was a more important source of information for teachers who teach in rural areas *for the organization of school activities and for the implementation of the teaching process during the pandemic*, compared to teachers who teach in urban areas.

The most important means of information, both for parents and students, is represented by social networks and applications (Facebook, Whatsapp, etc.), followed, by a long distance, by live communication.

The teachers who teach in the rural environment consider themselves more informed compared to the teachers who teach in the urban environment *in regards to the organization of the school activity, the implementation of the teaching process during the pandemic*.

Teachers who teach in rural areas appreciate the clarity of information about the organization of school activities and the implementation of the teaching process that they receive from state institutions as better, compared to teachers who teach in urban areas.

Information through *telephone calls* was a more important source for teachers teaching in rural areas compared to teachers in urban areas. *Email* was a more important source for teachers teaching in urban areas compared to teachers teaching in rural areas.

Informing parents about the teaching process via *e-mail*, as the main source of information, was used to a greater extent by teachers teaching in urban areas compared to teachers teaching in rural areas.

Informing students via *e-mail* and *live communication* were used as the main source of information to a greater extent by teachers teaching in urban areas compared to teachers teaching in rural areas.

Phone calls and *social media* ways were used as the main source of information to a greater extent by teachers teaching in rural areas compared to teachers teaching in urban areas.

Regarding *communication during the pandemic*, on the one hand, MEC, CCD and local authorities are considered more important sources of information *for the organization of school activity during the pandemic* for state-funded educational units compared to privately funded ones.

On the other hand, IŞJ is considered to be a more important source of information for privately financed educational units compared to those financed by the state.

There are no significant differences depending on the type of funding regarding the degree of information about the organization of school activity during the pandemic, the same being noted with regard to the clarity of the information received, as a teacher/director of the school, from state institutions.

Information via telephone calls, information via e-mail, information by direct communication and information by other means are more used in the case of educational units with state funding compared to those with private funding.

On the other hand, information through social networks and applications is more used in the case of educational units with private funding compared to those with state funding.

Informing parents through social networks was more used in private education than in state education, and information through live communication was more developed in state education than in private education. *Social media information* was used as the main source of information to a greater extent by teachers in private education compared to those in state education.

Also, *informing students through live communication* was used as the main source of information to a greater extent by teachers in public education compared to teachers in private education.

From the perspective of the education level, the *MEC* is a more important source of information for the organization of school activity during the pandemic for teachers who teach at the secondary or high school level, compared to teachers who teach at the pre-primary level.

IŞJ is a more important source of information for teachers who teach at the pre-primary level, compared to teachers who teach at the gymnasium or high school level.

CCD is more important for teachers teaching at the secondary level compared to teachers teaching at the pre-primary level.

Local authorities are a more important source of information for primary teachers compared to pre-primary teachers.

Teachers who teach at secondary level consider themselves more informed about the organization of school activities during the pandemic compared to teachers who teach at pre-primary level. Teachers who teach at the middle school level appreciate the clarity of

the information they receive as better compared to teachers who teach at the high school level.

Social media information about teaching during the pandemic is a more important source of information for middle school teachers compared to high school teachers.

E-mail information is a more important source of information for teachers who teach at the high school level compared to teachers who teach at the pre-primary, primary or secondary level.

Information through direct communication is a more important source of information for teachers teaching at the primary level compared to teachers teaching at the pre-primary or high school level.

There are no significant differences according to the *level of education* regarding *information by other means*.

Informing parents about the process of teaching during the pandemic through social media was more developed in the case of pre-primary teachers than in the case of primary teachers.

Informing parents by e-mail was more developed in the case of teachers teaching at the primary level than in the case of teachers teaching at the pre-primary or secondary level.

The situation of teachers who do not have direct communication with parents is found more among teachers who teach at the high school level, than in the case of teachers who teach at the primary level.

Informing students about the teaching process during the pandemic through phone calls was more used in the case of teachers teaching at the primary level than in the case of teachers teaching at the high school level. *Informing students through social media* was more used by teachers teaching at the pre-primary level than by teachers teaching at the primary level.

Informing students through live communication was more developed in the case of teachers teaching at the primary level than in the case of teachers teaching at the pre-primary level.

According to the function criterion, IŞJ is considered to be a source of information *for the organization of the school's activity and for the implementation of the teaching process during the pandemic* more important by principals, compared to teachers. Principals have a higher degree of information than teachers regarding the organization of school activity,

the implementation of the teaching process during the pandemic and the changes that occur. Principals value the clarity of this information to a greater extent than do teachers. There are no significant differences between principals and teachers in the case of *information via telephone calls* regarding the teaching process and other relevant aspects during the pandemic.

B. The teaching process during the COVID-19 pandemic

The online teaching process during the pandemic covers the ways of delivering materials and tasks or learning cues to students, the platforms used in online teaching and the challenges experienced in organizing the teaching process during the pandemic. With regard to online platforms or other means used in online teaching, their selection criteria are followed.

In connection with the implementation of the online teaching process, the participation in professional development activities before and after the onset of the pandemic, the bearing of costs for professional development after the onset of the pandemic and aspects of the management of the activity considered the most demanding are questioned.

Depending on the independent variable *the environment in which the school is located*, the provision of digital materials through digital technologies to students, as *a way of delivering learning materials to students*, is higher in the urban environment than in the rural environment.

The provision of printed materials to students is greater in rural than in urban environments, *the collection of printed materials by parents/guardians from teachers* is more used in rural than in urban environments.

The use of Adservio and Moodle platforms, e-mail or other means as *platforms used in online teaching* was more used in urban schools than in rural schools. The use of the Microsoft Team platform or Facebook in online teaching was higher in rural schools than in urban schools.

The criterion for choosing the platforms to be used for teaching online courses in the 2020/2021 school year *based on the recommendation of the institutions responsible for education* is more important in the case of teachers teaching in urban schools than in the case of teachers teaching in rural schools.

The criterion that *the whole school uses the same platform* for teaching online courses/ didactic activities in the 2020/2021 school year

is more important for teachers teaching in rural schools than for teachers teaching in urban schools.

The criterion based on *previous experience in using that online platform* is more important for teachers teaching in urban schools than for teachers teaching in rural schools.

Teachers teaching in urban schools participated in *digital skills development activities before the pandemic* to a greater extent than teachers teaching in rural schools.

Participation in *personally paid courses* is higher for teachers teaching in urban schools than for teachers teaching in rural schools.

There are no significant differences depending on the environment in which the school is located in the case of *participation in courses organized and paid for by the school*, there are no significant differences in the case of participation in *free courses* related to the development of digital skills *after* the onset of the pandemic.

Participation in exchanges of experience with colleagues who had digital skills is higher in the case of teachers teaching in urban schools than in the case of those teaching in rural areas.

Teachers who teach in urban schools personally endured participation in *digital skills development activities after the onset of the pandemic* to a greater extent than teachers who teach in rural schools.

There are no significant differences according to *the environment in which the school is located* regarding the *planning and organization of online teaching as the most demanding aspect of managing one's own activity*.

Planning and organizing online assessment is more stressful for teachers teaching in urban schools compared to teachers in rural schools.

Monitoring the assimilation of knowledge/acquisition of skills by students is a more stressful aspect for teachers teaching in urban schools than for teachers teaching in rural schools.

There are no significant differences depending on the *environment in which the school is located* in the case of *monitoring the implementation of measures related to the health of students and communication with parents*.

The organization of the teaching process, technical problems, the lack of digital skills of the teacher and the students, the lack of devices used at home are *challenges that rural teachers* experienced more, compared to urban teachers.

Providing *students with digital materials through digital technologies* is higher in private schools than in state schools, *providing students with printed materials* is higher in state schools than in private schools.

The take-up of printed materials by parents/guardians from teachers is higher in public schools than in private schools.

The use in online teaching of Microsoft Team platforms, Moodle, other means or Facebook are more used in state schools than in privately funded ones. The use in online teaching of the Zoom platform or email was higher in privately funded schools than in state schools.

The choice of platforms used to teach online courses in the 2020/2021 school year *based on the recommendation of the institutions responsible for education* is the more important criterion for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers in privately funded schools.

The whole-school-use-the-same-platform criterion is more important for teachers in privately funded schools than for teachers teaching in state-funded schools.

And the criterion *based on previous experience in using that online platform* is more important for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers in privately funded schools.

There are no significant differences according to *the type of funding of the school unit* in the case of *participation in digital skills development activities before the onset of the pandemic*.

Teachers in privately funded schools participated in *digital skills development activities after the pandemic* to a greater extent than teachers in state funded schools.

Participation in *free courses/tutorials* is higher for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers in privately funded schools.

Participation in *personally paid courses* is higher for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers teaching in privately funded schools.

Participation in *exchanges of experience and good practice with colleagues who had digital skills* is higher for teachers in privately funded schools than for teachers in state funded schools.

Teachers teaching in state-funded schools personally endured participation in *digital skills development activities after the pandemic* to a greater extent than teachers in privately funded schools.

There are no significant differences according to *the type of funding of the educational unit* in the challenge of *planning and organizing online teaching*.

Planning and organizing online assessment is more stressful for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers in privately funded schools.

There are no significant differences in the case of *monitoring the assimilation of knowledge/acquisition of skills by students*.

Monitoring the implementation of protective measures related to student health is more stressful for teachers in state-funded schools than for teachers in privately funded schools.

All challenges were experienced to a greater extent by teachers in privately funded schools compared to teachers in state funded schools regarding *communication with parents and Internet quality*.

Providing students with printed materials is a more developed way of *delivering learning materials to students* for pre-primary, primary and secondary teachers compared to high school teachers.

The situation in which *parents/guardians take printed materials from the teacher* is more common in the case of pre-primary, primary and secondary level teachers, compared to high school level teachers.

There are no significant differences according to the level of education regarding the use of the *ZOOM platform*.

The use of the Microsoft Team platform is found more in the practice of teachers who teach at the middle and high school level, compared to teachers who teach at the pre-primary and primary levels.

The Moodle platform in online teaching is more used by teachers who teach at the high school level, compared to teachers who teach at the pre-primary level.

Providing students with digital materials through digital technologies is more developed in the case of teachers with the second degree, compared to teachers with a final certificate.

Providing students with printed materials is more used by beginning teachers, compared to teachers with final, second degree or first degree.

It is more common among teachers with a final degree, compared to teachers with a second degree.

The situation in which the *parents/guardians take printed materials from the teacher* is the more used method in the case of beginning teachers, compared to teachers with the second degree.

The use of the *ZOOM platform* in online teaching is more developed in the case of second-degree teachers, compared to debutante or permanent teachers.

The use of the *Adservio platform* in online teaching is more common in the case of teachers with the first degree, compared to teachers with a final degree.

The *Microsoft Team platform* in online teaching is more used in the case of teachers with first degree, compared to teachers with final or second degree.

The *Moodle platform* is more used in online teaching in the case of teachers with first degree, compared to teachers with final or second degree.

The use of e-mail in online teaching is more common in the practice of teachers with first degree, compared to teachers with final or second degree.

The use of other means in online teaching is more used in the case of teachers with the first degree, compared to teachers with a final degree.

Facebook is more used in online teaching practice by teachers with first degree, compared to teachers with final or second degree.

Teachers with first degree participated in *digital skills development activities before* the pandemic to a greater extent than those with second degrees, with final degrees or beginners.

Those with second degrees more than those with final or beginners.

Teachers with the first degree declare that they have participated in *professional development activities related to the development of digital skills after* the onset of the pandemic to a greater extent than those with a final degree or beginners.

Participation in *free courses related to the development of digital skills after* the onset of the pandemic is higher in the case of first-degree teachers than in the case of novice teachers.

Participation in *personally paid courses* is higher in the case of first-degree teachers than in the case of novice or permanent teachers.

The participation in *exchanges of experience and good practices with colleagues who had digital skills* is higher in the case of teachers with the second degree than in the case of beginning teachers or teachers with a final degree.

Planning and organizing online teaching is a more stressful/demanding aspect for second-degree teachers compared to first-degree teachers.

Planning and organizing the online assessments is a more stressful/demanding aspect for teachers with a first degree than for teachers with a final degree.

Monitoring the assimilation of knowledge/acquisition of competences by students is a more stressful/demanding aspect for first-degree teachers than for novice teachers.

Monitoring the implementation of protective measures related to students' health is a more stressful/demanding aspect for first degree teachers than for second degree teachers.

Communication with parents is a more stressful/demanding aspect for teachers with the first degree than for teachers with a final degree.

The quality of the Internet is a more stressful/demanding aspect for teachers with a final degree than for teachers with a first degree.

There are no significant differences according to the *teaching degree* regarding the *challenges experienced in organizing the teaching process during the pandemic*: technical problems, the lack of digital skills of the teacher and the lack of digital skills of the students.

However, there are significant differences in the *lack of devices that students can use at home*. It is felt more by *beginning teachers*, compared to qualified teachers, or those with a second degree or first degree.

Providing students with materials through digital technologies is a more developed practice for teachers in schools with 51-100 employees compared to teachers in schools with less than 20 employees.

Providing students with printed materials is more common among teachers working in schools with 21-50 employees compared to teachers in schools with less than 20 employees.

There are no significant differences according to *the number of staff in the school* in terms of the extent to which *parents/guardians take printed materials from the teacher*.

The choice of online platforms to be used for teaching didactic activities in the school year 2020/2021 *based on the recommendation of the institutions responsible for education* is a more important criterion for teachers in schools with 51-100 employees.

The analysis is compared to the case of teachers who teach in schools with 21-50 employees or less than 20 employees.

The criterion *based on previous experience using a particular online platform* is more important for teachers in schools with more than 100 employees than for teachers in schools with 21-50 employees.

Technical problems, the teacher's lack of digital skills, are more common among teachers who teach in schools with less than 20 employees, compared to teachers in schools with between 21-50 employees, 51-100 employees or more than 100 employees.

Students' lack of digital skills is more common in schools with less than 20 employees compared to schools with 21-50 employees, 51-100 employees or more than 100 employees.

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